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CHALLENGES TO MAINTAIN SERVICES QUALITY IN BANKS FOR CUSTOMER RETENTION: AN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

Bank plays an important role in the economic development of a country. It is financial institution that accepts deposits and channels those deposits into lending activities either directly or through capital markets. A bank connects customers which have capital deficits to those customers with capital surpluses. This industry is facing certain challenges i.e. service quality, customer satisfaction, customer retention and customer reliability. A customer service has become therefore very important and significant especially in the financial business sector. As Indian public and private banks continue to provide an increasing number of financial services and products, they confront the challenge of coordinating these different frameworks into a coherent, efficient infrastructure, while conveying the maximum customer services and accommodating while not revealing their customers to the bank's internal system integration issues. This paper will explain the service quality challenges of banks to retain its customers.

Key words: Customer service, service quality, public and private banks, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction and financial institution.

Introduction:

In the service industry, successful companies need more than just a competitive advantage in customer service. They need to have unwavering loyalty from their customers. The way for offering world-class service is to know and reply according to the expectations of the customers. This is often as a result of customers evaluates perceptions to the expectations once judging the nature or quality of a firm's providing services (Parasuraman et al., 1988). The banking industry (which is part of the global service industry) not only plays a leading role within the financial system in a country but also has an important socio-economic function. Financial institutions particularly banks encourage economic advancement and it is the main aim of the government to build an efficient, viable and a steady economy, banking industry will support each the requirement of the real economy and also the socio-economic goals of the country. The banking industry offers short term as well as long term funds for investment. Banks provide liquidity on interest to investors through the present current account and stretch out credit and also liquidity to their borrowers through lines of credit (Kashyap et al., 1999). Payne (1995) has indicated that services firms devote most of their resources to attracting new customer but few take equal trouble to retain existing customer. The effect of longevity and profiles can be explained by several factors:

- Acquiring new customers costs more than retaining an existing on. The cost of acquiring a new customer is incurred only at the beginning of the relationship, thus longer the relationship the lower the amortized cost of acquisition. A long-term customer tends to be fewer prices sensitive pertaining higher prices to be charged.
- Long term, satisfied customers are likely to provide free, word of mouth advertising and referrals.
- Improved customer retention can also lead to an increased employee retention, which feeds, back into even greater customer longevity.

From the above one can conclude that it is more economical and beneficial for a service firm to retain customer.

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Focus groups unambiguously have upheld the opinion that the way for ensuring better service quality is meeting or surpassing what customers expecting from the services.

According to Seaman (1998) customer “who continue doing business with a company because of the service they receive will also spend money on other product and services within the same company”. Payne (1995) argues that the existing idea behind retentive customers has been sustaining quality. Research under taken in the financial services sector, indicates that quality programs no longer have the power to keep customers satisfied. This research suggests that quality is not always the major determinants of customer turnover.

Payne (1995) identifies the following four primary causes

- Rate increases;
- Competitive solicitation;
- Service deficiency, and
- Poor reputation.

Seaman (1998) has done an empirical investigation on the factors that influence the loyalty of customers, and customer-and employee turnover and has found the following eight main concerns relating to service factors for banks:

- Price-Customer view service charges as excessive.
- Inconvenience- branches and automatic teller machines are not always conveniently located hours of business are not always convenient. Customer must wait for appointments and for service, while some counters remain unmanned.
- Service failure – constant mistakes on customer accounts and system failure annoy customers.
- Service delivery – staff have a reluctant attitude to customer care and are unfriendly. They are unsympathetic and unprofessional and appear unqualified, as they do not know what products the banks offers.
- Reaction failure- staff reacts negatively when service fails, or does not react at all, or one unwilling to assist.
- Competitors – Customers experience that services of other banks are better.
- Ethical concerns- security is lacking at ATMs (Automatic Teller Machines) and in banking halls, which are found to be overcrowded. Customers’ accounts are moved to other branches without their permission.

Review of Studies:

The importance of quality to business outcomes is now well established in the academic literature. It has been exhibited that higher quality leads to higher stock prices, higher company performance, and better market worth of the firm. In the customer satisfaction/service quality enclosures, group market studies have shown that higher customer satisfaction results higher financial returns (Hallowell, 1996). The mechanisms by which this happens are clear. Quality enhancement programs generate specific change endeavor which create positive results by either sinking expenses or increasing revenues. The way in which service enhancement efforts yield expended incomes is sometimes control to be a series of effects (Zeithaml et al., 1996).

Customer satisfaction is another necessary facet for service organizations and is extremely associated with service quality (Bolton and Drew, 1991and Spreng & MacKoy, 1996). Presently, customers confront a growing variety of alternative within the products and services they can buy. They are determining their choice on the reason of their view of quality, service and value. Organizations need to comprehend the determinants of customer value and satisfaction. Customer-delivered worth is the variation among total customer worth and total customer cost. Customers can usually choose the offer that maximizes the delivered value.

Expanded customer satisfaction prompts behavioral results, like assurance, objective to stay (customer retention), formulation of a reciprocally pleasing relationship between the service supplier and the consumers/user, accumulated customer tolerance for service malfunctioning and positive word-of-mouth advertising about the organization (Gounaris et al., 2003; Reichheld, 1996; Newman, 2001). Only customer-oriented companies can deliver superior quality to their targeted customers will succeed in the market. Those organizations will be proficient at developing customers, not just developing products. They will be skillful in promotion designing, not just product building.

“Service quality has been associated with customer satisfaction within the banking industry” (Avkiran, 1994). Banks now identify that offering quality service to customers is essential for success and survival in today's global and competitive banking environment (Lewis and Pescetto, 1996). Research has shown that satisfying customers is not enough to retain them because even satisfied customers ‘defect’ at a high rate in many industries (Schneider and Bowen, 1999).

Problem Statement: How can financial institution improve service quality?

Sub Problems:

- How to solve service breakdowns by the financial institutions?
- How to retain customers after service breakdowns has occurred?
- What is service quality and how to apply it to obtain service excellence?

Research Methodology

The methodology employed in obtaining information about customer satisfaction, service quality and customer loyalty in banking through the studies conducted by different researcher. This study mainly based on secondary information.

Objective of the study

- To know the factors affecting the level of customers' satisfaction of Indian Banks.
- To determine the dimensions of service quality of Indian Banks.
- To study challenges faced by banks in maintaining the service quality for its customers.

Measurement of Service Quality

The measurement of service quality creates similar benefits and difficulties to that of satisfaction. According to accepted theory, satisfaction arises from the positive judgment of service quality received and cost incurred. Two major model of service quality exist.

SERVQUAL the SERVQUAL

Instrument is a questionnaire designed by Parasuraman and Zeithaml and Berry based on two principles;

- Customer’s judgment of service quality is comparing perception with their expectations.
- These judgments are made over five quality dimensions such as reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness. The questionnaire uses a Likert scale to gain customer rating of both expected service and perceived service on each of these dimensions. Quality scores are then derived by subtracting expected from perceived quality rating scores likewise be weighted to replicate the significance that customers place on every item

SERVPERF

- This completing model disputes the two key principles underpinning the SERVPERF. The inclusion of expectations among the estimation of service quality is ideal situation importantly, and from a critical standpoint it diminishes from the reliability of quality rating. Furthermore, the five dimensions of quality covers. They believe the measuring perceptions of quality alone and also recommended that each industry develops its own understanding of the quality dimensions as perceived by its customers.
- This technique underlying following themes can be suggested;
- Service quality perceptions result from a comparison of customer expectations with actual performance. Quality assessments are not prepared exclusively on the consequence of a service; they too involve assessment of the process of service delivery.

Customer expectation as a challenge for Indian Banks

The Indian banking sector continues to face some structural challenges. We have a comparatively a vast number of banks, some of them are inadequate in size and scale of operations. On the restrictive facade, alignment with worldwide improvement in banking supervision is a centre space for both supervisory body and banks. The new worldwide capital standards oblige an abnormal state of refinement in risk management, information systems, and technology which would pose a challenge for several contributors in the Indian banking sector. The profound and sometimes painful procedure of streamlining in the Indian economy and Indian industry has resulted in asset quality issues for the banking sector; while huge advancement is being made particularly in this area, a lot of work towards determination of those legacy problems still has to be done.

The Indian banking sector, in this manner has an energizing point in its development. The opportunities are immense – to enter new businesses and new markets, to expand better approach of working, to enhance efficiency, and to convey larger amounts of customer service. The process of modification and restructuring that has to be experienced to maximize by these opportunities raise a challenge for several banks. The Indian banking sector is faced with multiple and concurrent challenges such as expanded competition, rising customer expectations, and reducing customer reliability.

The banking industry is also changing at a phenomenal speed. Whereas at the one end, we have large number of savers and investors who still don't use the bank, another portion keeps on managing an account with a physical branch and flip side of the range, the customers are getting to be acquainted with ATMs, e-banking, and cashless economy. This demonstrates the large potential for market growth. The exponential development for the business comes from being able to handle as wide a range of this spectrum as possible. In this complex and fast shift in environment, the only sustainable competitive advantage is to give the customer an optimum blend of technology and traditional service. As banks build their procedure for giving customers access to their financial records through different propelled services like mobile banking, e-banking, and net banking, they ought to additionally view this developing stage as a potential impetus for creating operational efficiencies and as a vehicle for new source of revenue. Banking industry's opportunities includes

- A growing economy
- Banking deregulation
- Increased client borrowing
- An increase in the number of banks
- An increase in the money supply
- Low government-set credit rates and
- Larger customer checking account balances

Developing nations like India, contains an immense variety of individuals who don't have access to banking services because of scattered and fragmented areas. However if we tend to remark those individuals who are benefitting banking services, their expectations are elevated as the level of services are expanding

because of the appearance of Information Technology and colossal rivalry among the services and products/services provided by totally diverse banks. Since, majority of foreign banks are playing in Indian market, the quantity of services of offered has accumulated and banks have laid emphasis on meeting the customer expectations. India's banking sector has created quick strides in improving and positioning itself to the new competitive business surroundings. The numerous challenges confronted by banks now-a-days are on a way to deal with competitive forces and strengthen their financial records. Today, banks are unarticulated with burden of NPA's. It is rightly felt that these contaminated debts, if not recouped, can rag the terribly crucial for the banks.

Definition to the Concepts

Services

Collier, (1987:4-8), defines service management as follows: "Service management is the ability to conceive and design service packages and service delivery systems, to create a corporate culture through leadership and knowledge that fulfils some client needs, to manage the growth and daily activities of the service organization as effectively and efficiently as possible.

The question that arises is what services are? Collier also defines service as: "A bundle of explicit and implicit advantages performed with a supporting facility and using facilitating goods or products. A service has tangible (high goods content) and intangible (low goods content) attributes." Service management is the ability of simultaneously executing service marketing and service operations activities when providing the service

Service quality

According to Gronroos (1982) described the total service quality as customers perceptions of difference between the expected service and the perceived service.

Parasuraman et.al (1985) defines service quality as the comparison between customer expectation and perceptions of service. They advised three basic premises for service quality:

- (1) Service quality is tough for the purchaser to assess than product quality.
- (2) Service quality perceptions result from a evaluation of expectations with actual service performance, and
- (3) Quality evaluations are not made exclusively on the outcome of service; they also involved evaluations of the process of service process of service delivery.

Five gaps are listed below:

- Gap -1, Consumer expectation – Management perception gap: Management may have inaccurate perceptions of what consumers actually expect. It necessitates the suitable management processes, market analysis tools.
- Gap-2, Service quality specification gap: There may be an inability on the part of the management to translate customer expectations into service quality specifications. This gap relates to aspect of service design.
- Gap-3, Service delivery gap: Guidelines for service delivery do not promise top quality service delivery or performance. Reasons for this include absence of adequate support for the frontline staffs, process issues, or frontline/contact staffs performance variability.
- Gap-4, External communication gap: Customers expectations formed by the external communications of a company.
- Gap-5, Expected service – perceived service gap: Perceived quality of service depends upon the nature of the gaps related with marketing, design and delivery of services.

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Dimensions of Service Quality

Dimensions and Definition	Examples of specific questions raised by customers
Tangibles: Appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel and communication materials	Are the banks facilities attractive? Is my stockbroker dressed appropriately? Is my credit card statement easy to understand? Do the tools used by the repair person look modern?
Reliability: Ability to perform the promised service dependability and accurately.	When the loan officer says she will call me back in 15 minutes, does she do so? Does the stockbroker follow my exact instructions to buy and sell? Is my credit card statement free of errors? Is my washing machine repaired right the first time?
Responsiveness: Willingness to help customers and provide prompt service.	When there is a problem with my bank statement, will the bank resolve the matter quickly? Is my stockholder willing to answer my questions? Are charges for returned merchandise credited to my account promptly? Is the repair firm willing to give me specific time when the repair person will show up?
Competence: Possession of the required skills and knowledge to perform the service.	Is the bank employee ready to process my transactions without fumble around? Does my brokerage firm have the research capabilities to track market developments accurately? Does the repair person appear to know what he is doing?
Courtesy: Politeness, respect, consideration and friendliness of contact personnel.	Does the bank teller have pleasant demeanor? Does my broker refrain from acting busy or being rude when I ask questions? Are the telephone operators in the credit card company consistently polite when answering my calls? Does the repair person take off his muddy shoes before stepping on my carpet?
Credibility: Trustworthiness, believability, honest of the service provider.	Does the Bank Have good reputation? Does my broker refrain from pressuring me to buy? Does my credit card company consistent with the services provided charge the interest rates/fees? Does the repair firm guarantee its services?
Security: Freedom from danger risks or doubt.	Is it safe for me to use the bank automatic teller machines? Does my brokerage firm know where my stock certificate is? Is my credit card safe from unauthorized use? Can I be confident that the repair job was done properly?
Access: Approachability and ease of contact.	How is it for me to talk to senior bank officials when I have a problem? Is it easy to get through to my broker over the telephone? Does the credit card company have 24- hour, toll-free telephone number? Is the repair service facility conveniently located?
Communication: Keeping customers formed in language they can understand and listening to them.	Can the loan officer explain clearly the various charges related to the mortgage loan? Does my broker avoid using technical jargon? When I call my credit card company, are they willing to listen to me? Does the repair firm call when they are unable to keep a scheduled repair appointment?
Understanding the customer: Making the effort to know customers and their needs.	Does someone in my bank recognize me as a regular customer? Does my broker try to determine what my specific financial objectives are? Is the credit limit set by my credit card company consistent with what I can offered (i.e. neither too high not too low.)? Is the repair firm willing to be flexible enough to accommodate my schedule?

Source: Adopted from Zeithmal *et.al* (1990:21)

Public Sector Banks

Most of the public sector banks feel that they face a big challenge in providing “quick service” to the customer and the customer’s attitude changes and are very difficult to handle. Customer get irritated when there is no quality response and quick service. Banks find hardships while communicating with the customers, as there is a communication gap. The banks need to be efficiently trained on a common platform for effective communication.

Private Banks

Private Banks finds difficulties in delivering speedy services. It is also very intricate for the customers to know the rules and regulations about the bank without any confusion. Customers lose their patience when they are not getting quick reply and services from the banks. A couple of different bankers also feel that persuading customers for loan sanctioning and loan collecting is another big deal.

Importance of Service quality in Banks

Increasing competition, highly educated customers and increase in standard of living forcing many businesses to review their customer strategy. Many business firms are channeling more efforts to retain existing customers rather than acquire new ones since the cost of acquiring new customer is greater than cost of retaining existing customers.

Conclusion

Over the years, it has been observed that clouds of trepidation and drops of growth are two important phenomena of business, which regularly changes in several sets of conditions. The pre and post liberalization era has witnessed a variety of environmental revolutions that specifically influences the abovementioned phenomena. It is apparent that post liberalization era has spread new shades of development in India, however at the same time it is also posed some difficulties. This paper discusses the various challenges of banks service quality, customer satisfaction, customer’s retention and customer loyalty. The biggest challenge for banking industry is to serve the mass and huge market of India. Now the organizations get to be customer driven than product driven. The better we comprehend our customers, the more fruitful we will be in addressing their needs and wants. So as to relive abovementioned difficulties banks must cut their cost of services. Another perspective to experience the difficulties is product differentiation. Apart from traditional banking services, banks must focuses on product development, so that they can compete in extent of competition. Technology enhancement is a foreseeable aspect to face the challenges. The consumer awareness level is significantly higher as compared to previous years. Now-a-days they need internet banking, mobile banking, and ATM services and banks needs to be more focuses on up gradation of these services. .

In the modern marketing customer satisfactions is of supreme importance. The study on service quality in selected banks is measured in five dimensions by using SERVQUAL scale developed by Parasuraman et al (1988). The number of responses in the present research reveals that there exists a small perceptual difference regarding overall service quality with the respective banks. The respondents of both the banks (public and private banks) basically focus on the employees of the banks for enhancing customer satisfaction whereas the banks have more concentration on the tangible aspect such as automation, physical amenities and so on to attract and retain the customers. The dimensions like Reliability, Responsiveness and Assurance are found to be the most vital and strategic determinants of service quality and customer satisfaction for both public and private sector banks. If any financial institutions or banks need to maintain customers on a long term basis, bankers ought to work towards 100% customer satisfaction that consequently encourage customer delight.

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